

TEACHING METHODOLOGIES AND STUDENT SUCCESS: A COMPARISON BETWEEN COURSES IN CIVIL ENGINEERING

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Abstract: *This article analyzes and compares the pedagogical approaches used in Surveying and Construction Drawing course units within the Civil Engineering program, by evaluating their impact on class attendance and students' academic success. The Surveying course unit stands out due to its inclusion of practical fieldwork in real-world scenarios, an experiential approach that integrates theoretical and practical knowledge while fostering greater student engagement and motivation. The results show that the Surveying course unit has higher pass rates and greater student participation in classes across all analyzed academic years compared to the Construction Drawing course unit. This study highlights the need to rethink pedagogical strategies to optimize academic success and better prepare future civil engineers for the challenges of today's job market.*

Keywords: *Teaching Civil Engineering; Active Methodologies; Experiential Learning; Academic Success; Student Motivation*

1. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, civil engineering education faces the challenge of balancing a solid academic foundation with the need to prepare students for a constantly evolving job market (Ovtšarenko, Makuteniene, & Timinskas, 2020). The civil engineering sector requires professionals with strong theoretical and technical skills, the ability to adapt to new technologies, and proficiency in increasingly complex and ever-changing tools (Guerra & Rodriguez-Mesa, 2021). In addition to these skills, critical thinking and problem-solving abilities are essential to addressing the challenges inherent to this field (Paredes & Herrera, 2020). Competencies such as leadership, teamwork, communication, and efficient resource management are indispensable for the effective practice of the profession.

To meet these demands, civil engineering education has evolved to include more active methodologies, such as problem- or project-based learning (Gavin, 2011; Tan, Xu, Chen, Deng, & Wang, 2024), the integration of real-world case studies (Zuwala & Sztekler, 2018), simulations (Magana et al., 2021) experiential learning (Jamison, Fuher, Wang, & Huang-Saad, 2022), or collaborative learning (van Helden, Zandbergen, Specht, & Gill, 2023). These approaches enable a more effective connection between theoretical knowledge and its practical application, facilitating students' adaptation to the specific demands of professional practice. Simultaneously, they contribute to the development of transversal skills such as effective communication, critical and creative problem-solving, and teamwork. Equally

important is the impact of these practices on fostering student motivation, increasing academic success, and reducing dropout rates in higher education.

In this context, one of the main challenges is to integrate traditional methods, which ensure the transmission of essential theoretical and technical foundations, with innovative approaches that foster practical and transversal skills aligned with market demands and the sector's context (Vemury, Heidrich, Thorpe, & Crosbie, 2018).

This article discusses and compares the approaches to the courses units of Surveying and Construction Drawing, which play a central role in the education of civil engineers.

The Surveying course unit aims to prepare students to perform precise measurements, use these results to create accurate terrain models, and interpret the geometric features of land. The use of georeferenced information, in the form of maps and topographic charts, is essential for territorial planning and engineering project design tasks. Covering both theoretical and practical foundations, the course teaches the use of surveying equipment, thereby contributing to more informed technical decision-making and greater efficiency in projects.

The Construction Drawing course unit aims to equip students with technical and practical skills for the development, interpretation, and analysis of construction projects. It emphasizes mastery of the standards and graphical representations used in engineering, with a focus on the precision and clarity of technical drawings applied to the sector.

These courses share a common goal: to develop essential skills for the education of civil engineers. They combine theoretical knowledge with practical application, emphasizing the interpretation and analysis of technical data relevant to the planning and execution of engineering projects.

The adoption of effective pedagogical methodologies is essential for fostering student motivation—a crucial factor for learning - with a direct impact on academic success and skill development (Cantero-Chinchilla, Díaz-Martín, Marín, & Gualda, 2019). Motivated students actively participate in classes and engage more enthusiastically with the proposed activities, creating a dynamic learning environment. This engagement not only promotes a deeper and longer-lasting understanding of the content but also creates conditions for instructors to introduce more creative and stimulating challenges, thereby enhancing students' academic and personal growth (Blanco, Gonzalez, Sánchez-Lite, & Sebastián, 2017).

This article aims to analyze and compare the pedagogical approaches used in each of the courses, assessing their impact on academic performance and students' preparation to face market challenges. Thus, this study seeks to answer the following research question: "How do the pedagogical strategies used in the Surveying and Construction Drawing courses influence academic success and the integration of professional skills in the context of Civil Engineering education?"

The analysis will identify opportunities for improvement in the adopted pedagogical strategies, contributing to a more successful academic education better aligned with the contemporary demands of the sector.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study focused on the Surveying and Construction Drawing course units of the Civil Engineering program at the Polytechnic Institute of Porto's ISEP during 2016/2017, 2017/2018, 2018/2019, 2022/2023, and 2023/2024 academic years, excluding the years impacted by the Covid-19 pandemic. The study adopts a descriptive and comparative methodology aimed at evaluating the impact of the pedagogical strategies employed in each course.

For data collection, information such as pass rates, class attendance rates (divided between theoretical and practical classes), levels of active participation in proposed activities, and retention indicators (based on the number of repeated enrollments) were analyzed. The institution referenced has a management system for academic activities, an institutional portal, which serves as the data source for this study.

The pedagogical methodologies applied in each course unit are described below.

In the Surveying course unit, there are three types of classes: theoretical, theoretical-practical, and laboratory practical; each employing distinct teaching-learning methodologies. In theoretical classes, expository and interrogative methods are used, and, when appropriate, various active method techniques are also employed. In theoretical-practical classes, active method techniques, such as case studies and problem-based learning, are predominantly used. In laboratory practical classes, experiential learning methodologies are employed, involving practical fieldwork and the preparation of topographic maps. Students, working in groups, carry out measures and prepare corresponding reports. This approach allows students to apply theoretical knowledge acquired in the classroom to real-world contexts.

In the Construction Drawing course unit, there are two types of classes: theoretical and theoretical-practical, with distinct teaching-learning methodologies. In theoretical classes, the expository method is used, and when appropriate, interrogative and active methods are also applied. In theoretical-practical classes, active methods such as practical case studies and problem-based learning are predominantly used. Whenever appropriate, challenges are presented to be solved in groups through consensus-building among group members.

From the comparative analysis of the pedagogical strategies employed, particularly in practical classes, it is observed that active methodologies such as problem-based learning and case studies are used in both courses. However, the Surveying course unit is distinguished by the inclusion of the experiential approach implemented through the analysis of real situations. This includes conducting practical fieldwork, using the results obtained to create accurate terrain models. These activities encompass both field and office work, involving site recognition, planning the work to be performed, using surveying equipment (with the inherent organization of the work team and precise measurement recording), and, after fieldwork, processing the results and performing calculations, followed by the preparation of corresponding topographic maps and reflection on the results.

The described approach enables an efficient connection between theoretical knowledge and its practical application. The proposed activities, which include defining the "topographic framework," planning the work to be carried out, and organizing teamwork to execute various tasks, help students develop skills in effective communication, teamwork, problem-solving, and critical decision-making, adapting to new situations and demands. Students' active participation and involvement in the proposed tasks foster stimulating challenges that encourage the integration of practical skills essential for professional practice.

To evaluate the impact of the pedagogical strategies adopted in each course on students' academic performance, Table 1 presents data on pass rates and attendance rates by class type; and Table 2 provides retention indicators (based on the number of repeated enrollments).

Table 1: Pass rates and attendance rates for theoretical (T), theoretical-practical (TP), and laboratory practical (PL) classes in different academic years for the Construction Drawing and Surveying courses.

Academic Year	Construction Drawing			Surveying			Pass (%)
	Attendance (%)		Pass (%)	Attendance (%)			
	T	TP		T	TP	PL	
16-17	25	43	27	19	54	53	68
17-18	29	41	31	20	47	49	48
18-19	36	54	38	73	66	70	61
22-23	31	51	21	13	50	50	51
23-24	30	48	33	20	51	62	42

Regarding pass rates, comparing the percentage of students who passed Construction Drawing and Surveying, it is evident that the latter consistently shows significantly higher pass rates across all academic years, highlighting better academic performance in this course.

Analyzing student participation in terms of attendance rates for theoretical and practical classes in each course, it is observed that attendance rates for theoretical classes are almost always lower in Surveying. However, the opposite occurs in practical classes, where attendance rates are consistently higher in Surveying.

When considering attendance rates and pass rates, there is generally a trend where higher attendance rates correspond to higher pass rates.

The levels of active participation in proposed activities, assessed based on the frequency of participation in discussions, fieldwork, and in-class exercises, are perceived by the instructor as significantly higher in the Surveying course. In this course, students appear more engaged and demonstrate greater interest in completing the proposed tasks.

Analyzing the number of enrollments required to pass the courses under study provides a complementary perspective on pass/fail rates. The information on retention indicators (based on the number of repeated enrollments) presented in Table 2 for Construction Drawing and Surveying clearly shows that the percentage of students enrolled in Surveying only once is higher. In contrast, the percentage of students enrolled in Construction Drawing only once is consistently below 60% of the total enrolled students.

These results can be interpreted based on the appropriateness of the adopted pedagogical approaches, suggesting the need to rethink the Construction Drawing course unit to reduce frequent failures and subsequent re-enrollments in later years.

Table 2: Number of enrollments (% of Students) in different academic years for the Construction Drawing and Surveying courses.

Academic Year	Number of enrollments (%)							
	Construction Drawing				Surveying			
	1	2	3	4 +	1	2	3	4 +
16-17	59	26	6	9	71	13	5	11
17-18	57	21	15	7	80	8	5	8
18-19	49	25	12	14	61	29	4	6
22-23	55	19	10	17	57	25	8	11
23-24	51	24	10	15	63	16	8	14

The analysis of the collected data suggests that the adoption of differentiated pedagogical approaches leads to equally differentiated levels of effectiveness and influences students' motivation and participation, contributing to improved academic success and the development of transversal skills.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The comparative analysis of the pedagogical approaches used in the Surveying and Construction Drawing course units suggests that differentiated approaches have a varied impact on academic performance and the development of transversal skills. In the Surveying course unit, the incorporation of the experiential approach, implemented through practical fieldwork in real-world scenarios, appears to facilitate a more effective integration of knowledge, greater student engagement, and higher academic success. The results show higher student participation rates in classes across all analyzed academic years, as well as higher pass rates.

This article highlights the need to rethink and adapt the pedagogical methodologies employed, ensuring the transmission of solid theoretical foundations while fostering practical and transversal skills and promoting academic success. Today's civil engineering education must adopt pedagogical approaches that contribute to training more aligned with the challenges and opportunities of the current job market.

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